

BEHIND THE GRADES

A Mindspace Project

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Behind The Grades is a student-led mental health initiative under the MindSpace project, aimed at addressing common psychological challenges faced by high schoolers, including stress, procrastination, and difficulty maintaining life balance. Through a Google Form survey with 126 respondents, the project collected qualitative and quantitative data focused on six key themes: procrastination, study-life balance, academic competition, loneliness, lack of motivation, and overthinking.

Findings reveal that students who struggle with procrastination often seek understanding rather than judgment, hoping others will recognize the deeper emotional roots beyond laziness. Those stressed by academic competition desire a growth-oriented environment instead of one driven by comparison. Across the areas of study-life balance, loneliness, and overthinking, students consistently express a need for empathetic listeners—trustworthy individuals who offer support without criticism. Notably, overthinkers particularly value reassurance that mistakes are acceptable and that they are not alone.

To conclude the project, the team will organize solution-focused interviews between student participants and mental health experts, offering personalized strategies to help students cope with their struggles in real-life contexts.

Keywords: mental health, high school students, procrastination, academic competition, loneliness, study-life balance, lack of motivation, overthinking, peer support, youth psychology, student well-being

Chapter 1 - Introduction

Academic demands on adolescents have intensified globally, with recent studies documenting significant relationships between academic stress, procrastination, and mental-health outcomes (Gao et al., 2023; González-Brignardello et al., 2023; Pérez-Jorge et al., 2024). For example, Gao et al. (2023) found that academic stress can lead to burnout via reduced self-efficacy among adolescents, while González-Brignardello et al. (2023) highlight how procrastination behaviours contribute to poorer well-being in youth. Earlier work by Lin & Huang (2013) links life stress directly to academic burnout in higher-education settings, suggesting that the phenomenon begins well before university.

In recent years, the academic environment in Vietnam has become increasingly competitive, often coming at the cost of many students' mental well-being. Unfortunately, it is common to notice that many students struggle to cope with the constant high expectations from schools, families, and themselves, resulting in burnout, anxiety, and feelings of isolation. To be specific, in Vietnam, over 60% of lower secondary school students reported feeling stressed about schoolwork, with academic pressure being one of the leading contributors to poor mental health among adolescents (UNICEF & MOET, 2023). Despite recent education reforms, students continue to face high expectations, rigid exam-oriented environments, and limited access to psychological support services in schools. These conditions create fertile ground for chronic stress and burnout to emerge early during formative academic years.

Global prevalence of anxiety, depression and other disorders among girls and boys aged 10-19 with mental disorders (2019).³

Age 10–19, girls

Age 10–19, boys

(UNICEF & MOET, 2023)

Most of the team in this research are also high schoolers who often struggle to balance their lives and academics, and wish to find at least a way to ease the unfortunate situation many students are currently facing. Together, despite different school backgrounds or age, we found MindSpace, aiming to help students manage stress, procrastination, and life balance through open conversations and practical mental awareness strategies. And our first project, “Behind The Grades,” does exactly that, acting as a way for many students to speak up about their lives behind all those grades on those white pieces of paper.

Chapter 2 - Methodology

We will collect primary data through a Google Form survey (see the appendix) to gain deeper insight into the problems students face.

The survey covers six major themes: procrastination, study-life balance, academic competition, loneliness, lack of motivation, and overthinking, to cover better all the common issues faced by students in Vietnam. However, the participant was asked to choose one theme they felt most comfortable with and relatable to share their personal experience.

Each theme contained 10 questions, combining both quantitative (scales, multiple-choice) and qualitative (open-ended reflections) formats. The survey was distributed online to participants aged 6 to 24, with a primary focus on high school students aged 15 to 17 across Vietnam.

We aim to collect a sample size of at least 120 responses to be able to analyse the issues more accurately and make a more representative conclusion with low bias. Demographic data, such as age and gender, were recorded for comparison and contextual understanding.

To ensure ethical research standards, participation was completely voluntary and anonymous, with no incentives offered unless otherwise stated. Our analytical approach is thematic grouping (organizing information, students around a central theme to enhance understanding).

This research follows the survey research framework proposed by Creswell (2014), focusing on a descriptive approach to understand students' experiences. The questionnaire was designed and distributed using Google Forms, ensuring anonymity and voluntary participation. In line with Cohen et al. (2018), ethical considerations were prioritized, and limitations such as sample representativeness and geographic concentration were acknowledged.

Chapter 3 - Findings & Discussion

3.1 Procrastination

Procrastination appears as one of the most frequent struggles among high school students. From the survey data, *Question 5: "How often do you procrastinate?"*, more than half of respondents reported experiencing procrastination "almost every day." *Question 6: "What do you usually procrastinate on?"*, particularly when dealing with homework, long-term projects, or even simple daily tasks. This habit tends to worsen during exam periods or when students face multiple deadlines simultaneously.

Students emphasized that procrastination is not simply laziness, but rather a complex emotional response to pressure. *Question 7: "What usually triggers your procrastination?"*, as one student clearly stated, "It's not laziness — it's more complex than that." The main causes include fear of failure or perfectionism, lack of motivation or energy, and constant distractions such as phones, social media, or messages. Others shared that they often feel overwhelmed by how big a task is or don't know where to start, revealing deeper struggles with self-doubt and time management.

Several responses reflected emotional conflict behind this behavior:

Question 9& 10: "How do you usually try to deal with procrastination?" / "Have you found anything that helps?"

"From my experience, I feel like discipline is a talent. I watched so many videos about how to solve procrastination, but none of them work for me."

"I do realize my procrastination and try to solve it, but it's still happening... when I finally followed the schedule and avoided procrastination, accidents jumped in and everything went back to zero."

These quotes show that students are aware of their problem but feel mentally stuck and emotionally drained. Many rely on temporary coping methods like pushing through last-minute, using to-do lists or Pomodoro timers, or avoiding the problem altogether. However, the repetition of phrases like *"I'm managing, but it's tiring"* and *"School takes up most of my time"* indicates that procrastination for many is a symptom of ongoing academic fatigue, not poor self-control.

Procrastination is a common struggle among high school students, affecting both emotions and academics. From Question 5, 71% said they procrastinate "almost every day." Question 6 showed that homework and assignments are delayed the most (77.4%), followed by studying for tests (64.5%) and daily tasks (61.3%). In Question 7, 90.3% reported that lack of motivation or energy triggers procrastination, showing it often comes from mental fatigue rather than laziness. Many also feel overwhelmed by task size or unsure where to start, reflecting self-doubt and time management struggles. From Questions 9 and 10, 58.1% try to push through and work last minute, but most find it ineffective.

Students suggested three main strategies: focusing on the most important tasks to reduce overwhelm, using tools like Google Calendar to plan and track deadlines, and occasionally distracting themselves from problems to reset mentally. These strategies help students manage workload, improve time awareness, and reduce emotional strain. Overall, overcoming procrastination requires a combination of practical planning, focused effort, and emotional care, making both academic performance and mental well-being more sustainable.

To deepen the understanding of procrastination among students, Burka and Yuen (2008) in their seminal work *Procrastination: Why You Do It, What to Do About It Now* identify key psychological roots behind avoidance behaviors—such as fear of failure, perfectionism, and difficulty with emotional self-regulation. Their framework emphasizes that procrastination is not merely a time-management issue, but a complex interaction between emotion, cognition, and behavior. The authors advocate for breaking down overwhelming tasks, adopting structured planning tools, and developing emotional awareness as essential steps to overcoming procrastination. This aligns strongly with the strategies proposed by the students in the survey. By prioritizing key tasks to reduce overwhelm, leveraging digital tools like Google Calendar, and incorporating mindful distractions to reset, students are intuitively applying many of the recommendations found in psychological research. These combined approaches—practical planning, self-awareness, and emotional self-care—create a more sustainable model for academic success and mental resilience.

3.2 Study-Life Balance

A recurring pattern in the responses is the difficulty students face in maintaining a healthy balance between study and personal life. *Question: "Do you think you have a healthy study-life balance?"* Many expressed that school dominates nearly all of their time, with one respondent repeatedly noting, *"School takes up most of my time."* This leaves little space for rest, hobbies, or social interaction. Even when opportunities for rest appear, students feel guilty for taking them — torn between needing a break and fearing they are "falling behind."

Common causes of imbalance include heavy academic workloads, tight deadlines, and external expectations from teachers or parents. Several students reported that they cannot say "no" to additional tasks or group projects, even when they already feel burned out. *Question: "How does this affect your health or emotions?"* As one student shared, *"I'm managing, but it's tiring,"* while another added, *"I'm constantly switching between guilt and burnout."* These responses reveal that the issue is not lack of motivation but rather the difficulty of finding time to recharge in an environment that rewards nonstop productivity.

Maintaining a healthy study-life balance is a major challenge for many students. In response to "Do you think you have a healthy study-life balance?", most reported that school dominates nearly all their time. One student repeatedly noted, "School takes up most of my time," leaving little space for rest, hobbies, or social interactions. Even when breaks are possible, students often feel guilty, torn between resting and fearing they are "falling behind."

The main causes of this imbalance include heavy academic workloads, tight deadlines, and external expectations from teachers and parents. Many students feel unable to say no to additional tasks or group projects, even when burned out. This constant pressure affects both mental and physical well-being. As one student shared, "I'm managing, but it's tiring," while another said, "I'm constantly switching between guilt and burnout." These responses show that the issue is not lack of motivation, but the difficulty of finding time to recharge in a culture that rewards nonstop productivity.

To address these challenges, students emphasized the importance of time management, setting boundaries, and prioritizing self-care. Strategies include scheduling regular breaks, engaging in hobbies, and openly communicating with teachers or peers when feeling overwhelmed. Creating a supportive environment where rest is accepted as part of success can help reduce stress and improve overall well-being.

Research has shown that life satisfaction among students is significantly influenced by anxiety and depression levels, as well as factors such as satisfaction with academic programs and socio-economic status (Serin, Serin, & Özbaş, 2010). In particular, higher anxiety and depressive symptoms are associated with lower levels of life satisfaction, underscoring the psychological burden that academic stress can impose on students. This reinforces the experiences shared by high school participants in this project, who described how academic overload, external expectations, and the inability to decline additional responsibilities contribute to emotional exhaustion. Their reflections—"I'm constantly switching between guilt and

burnout”—highlight the urgent need to address psychological well-being through better time management, boundary setting, and institutional support.

3.3 Academic Competition

Students feel pressure mostly during challenging times, e.g, during exams or during ranking, with some students who felt pressure at all times, even at times that they didn't want to. Various sources cause the pressure of academic competition; the most prominent source is from themselves, with 77.8% of the responders, with a desire to become the best. Other sources of pressure took up noticeable portions of all the responders when discussing academic competitions; namely, from peers, parental or family expectations, and from university preparation procedures (55.6, 44.4 and 44.4 percent respectively)

There are a lot of effects that academic pressure causes, which are mainly negative, but there is one positive effect that stands out against the others. The sole positive effect shows that people are feeling motivated to do better, with 66.7% of the responders feeling this way. The most notable negative impacts were anxiety, insecurity, and the feeling of being judged by their own grades. This is understandable, as today's society emphasizes the importance of grades and students use it as a metric to compare and undermine each other's abilities, which leads to decreased self-esteem in individuals.

Currently, students stress themselves by putting too much effort into reaching the top, or by quietly comparing themselves to others and feeling bad. This is not a healthy coping mechanism, and many students agree on a change in personal habits as well as external behaviors, such as more self-focus on personal progress, having open conversations about the emotional impacts on grades and embracing other people who celebrate the efforts of these students, such as teachers or peers.

As noted by Abernathy and Vineyard (2001), academic competitions in science often offer students not only recognition but also opportunities to develop self-efficacy, teamwork, and curiosity beyond standard classroom tasks. Their study found that participants frequently reported that contests were “fun,” intellectually stimulating, and a context where they could compare themselves with peers from other schools, thereby expanding their self-concept. In the #BehindTheGrades survey, many students perceived competition as a double-edged sword: while striving to outperform peers can stimulate motivation, it also creates pressure, over-identification with results, and emotional fatigue. This aligns with Abernathy & Vineyard's suggestion that, unless managed carefully, competitive settings may reinforce performance-anxiety and narrow definitions of success - highlighting the need for more inclusive, balanced academic cultures in Vietnamese high schools.

3.4 Loneliness

Half of all the responders in the form that opened up about their loneliness reported that they feel disconnected from others almost every day. These students stated that they feel empty with or without the presence of people around them, feeling left out and unseen by others, or do not feel like there is the right person to talk to. A lot of the responders felt lonely, mostly at school or

at home, especially at night while they're trying to sleep, and it has a negative impact on their overall well-being. Impacts include the deterioration of mental health, increased feelings of grogginess and demotivation, questioning of self, and students even attempting to hide their sense of loneliness.

Alleviations to the youth's loneliness are mostly reported as passive, with 83.3% of responders agreeing that someone checking in on them makes them feel less lonely. Other suggestions include a safe space to talk to without judgment, empathizing with others who are going through the same situation, or even reaching out to trusted adults, such as teachers or mentors who are genuinely concerned about other people's emotions.

The #BehindTheGrades survey responses resonate with broader research on adolescent loneliness. For instance, Gurşes et al. (2011) found that loneliness is prevalent among high school students and often influenced by gender, with female students reporting significantly higher levels of loneliness than males. Interestingly, they also noted that loneliness was not strongly correlated with accommodation type or academic achievement, suggesting that emotional well-being is shaped more by internal and social factors than by structural ones. Similarly, students in this project highlighted that their feelings of loneliness could be alleviated through simple emotional support—such as having someone check in, finding a safe space to talk, or connecting with empathetic peers and mentors. These parallels underscore the importance of emotional validation and social connection in addressing teenage loneliness.

3.5 Lack of Motivation & Overthinking

Most students feel demotivated at least a few times a week. Schoolwork feels the most tedious to deal with, although some students are also tired of getting up and starting the day, or feel exhausted trying to plan for their own future. Young students feel burnt out because their peers are doing better than they are, and there is no way that they can catch up to them. They tend to delay tasks or have guilty, pessimistic and self-accusing thoughts. This impacts their performance and health overall, such as affected deadlines and grades, irregularity of sleep schedules, and attempts to inhibit exhaustion. Solutions can come as smaller, more manageable goals, or knowing that they themselves are not the only ones struggling, or someone to check in and keep motivating the students.

Overthinking tends to occur in many different scenarios, for example, before and after social interactions, mainly about schoolwork, something small that goes wrong or external perceptions about themselves. It usually comes in the form of frequent reminiscence of the dreaded moments, indecisiveness or creating imaginary scenarios to rehearse what to do to answer the "what if" questions that are in their minds. Questions for the 'self', such as "what if I fail?" or "what if I make a mistake," are common among the modern generation's minds when overthinking is mentioned. As a result, students will feel emotionally drained, have trouble finishing tasks on time and falling asleep, and most prominently, feel anxious even when things are fine. Having someone to open up honestly would calm their overthinking minds, although applying strategies to slow down thought is also an effective solution that many responders have agreed to as well.

The reflections shared by students about their lack of motivation closely mirror findings in existing academic research. In a study by Hamada (2008), demotivation among Japanese teenagers is explored through both qualitative and quantitative methods. The study found that students often begin their academic journey with enthusiasm, but gradually lose motivation due to several factors such as pressure from grammar-heavy learning, lack of confidence, and comparison with peers. This aligns with the students' own expressions of burnout and self-doubt, especially when seeing others outperform them academically. Hamada also highlights how emotional states such as guilt and pessimism play a role in the demotivation cycle—echoed in student responses where they described feeling tired, guilty, or hopeless, which then leads to procrastination and disrupted sleep. Both sources point to the importance of setting smaller, achievable goals and having emotional support systems (such as check-ins) to rebuild motivation and resilience.

Chapter 4 - Student-Driven Solutions

Students shared a variety of ideas focusing on creating more supportive and understanding environments, rather than implementing large-scale or formal programs. Many emphasized the importance of safe spaces, both physical and emotional, where they could comfortably share their stress, anxiety, and personal challenges without fear of judgment or stigma. They expressed a desire for opportunities to speak openly in small, friendly groups where honesty and empathy are encouraged. A significant number of participants said they preferred anonymous or small-group discussions, as these formats made them feel more comfortable and secure than large workshops or formal counseling sessions. This reflects a strong desire for privacy, empathy, and peer connection, rather than top-down or institutionalized interventions. Another major theme highlighted by students was the need for balance, including better time management support, opportunities for non-academic rest, and reduced academic pressure. Many said that learning how to organize their study schedules more effectively would help them feel less overwhelmed. They also wanted more chances to rest, engage in creative or social activities, and recharge mentally and emotionally. Some offered practical suggestions, such as reducing workload or allowing more flexibility with deadlines. Overall, these responses show that students are not asking for grand or costly solutions; they simply want to be seen, heard, and understood in genuine and compassionate ways that reflect their real needs and daily experiences.

Chapter 5 - Limitations

Although the findings offer valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. The survey used a self-selected sample, which may have skewed results toward students who are already more interested or aware of mental health issues. Some participants did not complete all questions or skipped open-ended responses, leading to potential data gaps and reduced representativeness. In addition, the study did not include a control group or longitudinal tracking, making it difficult to assess changes over time or identify causal relationships. The varying depth

and expression of responses also affected data consistency. Therefore, while these findings shed light on important aspects of student mental health, they should be viewed as exploratory insights rather than definitive conclusions.

Chapter 6 - Conclusion & Call to Action

The “Behind The Grades” project highlights the complex and multifaceted mental health challenges faced by students in Vietnam, particularly high schoolers. Through survey responses from 126 participants, we found that struggles such as procrastination, difficulty maintaining a study-life balance, academic competition, loneliness, lack of motivation, and overthinking are prevalent and deeply interconnected. Many of these issues are not simply the result of laziness or lack of discipline, but stem from high academic expectations, self-pressure, and a need for emotional support.

A consistent theme across several struggles is the desire for understanding, trust, and non-judgmental communication. Whether students face overthinking, loneliness, or difficulty balancing their studies and personal life, they express a strong need to talk openly with someone they trust. Procrastination and lack of motivation often appear as symptoms of mental fatigue and pressure, rather than personal shortcomings. Similarly, academic competition, while sometimes motivating, frequently leads to anxiety, insecurity, and self-comparison, which can exacerbate other challenges.

Student-driven solutions emphasize creating safe spaces, fostering empathy, and supporting peer connections rather than relying solely on formal programs. Practical strategies such as time management, scheduling breaks, and focusing on personal growth were highlighted as effective ways to manage stress and improve overall well-being.

While this study has limitations due to self-selected sampling, voluntary participation, and the lack of longitudinal data, it provides valuable exploratory insights into the mental health needs of Vietnamese students. Overall, addressing these challenges requires a combination of emotional support, realistic academic expectations, and practical strategies for managing time and stress. By listening to students’ voices and incorporating their suggestions, schools, families, and communities can help create environments where students can thrive both academically and personally.

Appendix

Demographic Breakdown Table

CATEGORY	OPTIONS	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	% OF RESPONDENTS	AVERAGE SCHOOL EXPERIENCE RATING
AGE GROUP	6 - 11	2	1.8	6.0
	12 - 14	10	9.0	7.0
	15 - 17	80	72.1	7.4
	18 - 20	17	15.3	8.4
	21 - 23	1	0.9	6.0
	+24	2	1.8	9.0
GENDER	Male	33	29.7	7.5
	Female	70	63.1	7.7
	Others	3	2.7	7.3
	Prefer not to say	5	4.5	7.2

Sample Survey Questions

QUESTION	FOCUS TOPICS	RESPONSE TYPE	SUMMARY OF RESPONSES
<p>What do you usually procrastinate on?</p>	<p>Procrastination</p>	<p>Multiple-choice</p>	<p>1. Homework or assignments: This is the most common answer, selected by 24 respondents (77.4%).</p> <p>2. Studying for tests: This came in a close second, with 20 respondents (64.5%).</p> <p>3. Daily tasks (e.g., cleaning, organizing, etc.): Interestingly, this non-academic task was the third most frequent, with 19 respondents (61.3%).</p>
<p>How does this imbalance affect your overall well-being?</p>	<p>Study-life balance</p>	<p>Multiple-choice</p>	<p>1. I feel constantly stressed: This is the overwhelming top response, selected by 18 respondents (54.5%).</p> <p>2. I lose sleep or feel tired all the time: This is the second most common effect, chosen by 13 respondents (39.4%).</p> <p>3. I'm losing motivation for school: Selected by 11 respondents (33.3%).</p> <p>4. I've stopped enjoying things I used to love: Also selected by 11 respondents (33.3%).</p> <p>5. I feel emotionally drained or disengaged: Another key finding, selected by 11 respondents (33.3%).</p>

<p>How does academic competition make you feel?</p>	<p>Academic competition</p>	<p>Multiple-choice</p>	<p>The 9 respondents feel highly conflicted about academic competition. It is simultaneously a strong motivator ("pushes me to do better") for 6 (66.7%) of them and a source of deep insecurity ("Like I'm never enough") for the same number. Over half also report feeling anxious and judged based on their grades.</p>
<p>When do you feel the most lonely?</p>	<p>Loneliness</p>	<p>Multiple-choice</p>	<p>The clearest finding is that 100% of respondents (6 out of 6) feel the most lonely at night or when I'm trying to sleep.</p> <p>The next most common time for loneliness is at home, selected by 4 respondents (66.7%).</p> <p>Other times for loneliness are less frequent, all tied at 2 respondents (33.3%) each:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● During breaks or weekends ● In social situations ● When I scroll on social media <p>Finally, 3 respondents (50%) report feeling the most lonely at school</p>

<p>What do you often feel unmotivated to do?</p>	<p>Lack of Motivation</p>	<p>Multiple-choice</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procrastination: The most common thought is the intent to delay action, with 9 respondents (69.2%) thinking, "I'll do it later' - but then I don't." 2. Social Comparison: The second most frequent thought is a sense of inadequacy compared to others, with 6 respondents (46.2%) thinking, "Everyone else is doing better than me." <p>The remaining thoughts are much less frequent, each selected by only 2 respondents (15.4%):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "I'll never catch up anyway." ● "I wish someone could help me..." ● "I don't even think - I just shut down." <p>The least common thought, selected by only 1 respondent (7.7%), is "What's the point?" The final unlisted option was also selected by 1 respondent (7.7%).</p>
<p>What would help you feel more motivated or supported?</p>	<p>Student-Driven Solutions</p>	<p>Multiple-choice</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Smaller, manageable goals 2. Encouragement that doesn't feel like pressure <p>The next most common needs were tied, each selected by 5 respondents (38.5%):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Someone checking in with me regularly ● A better balance between rest and work ● Just knowing I'm not the only one struggling

			Notably, 3 respondents selected "I'm not sure yet" (23.1%), and 1 respondent (7.7%) chose the need for "More freedom to rest without guilt.
How has this impacted your life or mindset?	Limitations	Multiple-choice	<p>The impact is severe and unanimous across three key negative areas, each selected by both respondents (100%):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparison: "I compare myself to more 'successful' people." • Worry: "I'm worried about my university." • Inadequacy: "I feel like I'm not doing 'enough'." <p>Additionally, 1 respondent (50%) reported losing motivation for activities. Notably, 0% of respondents felt constantly tired, lacked enough time to rest, or felt like they were always performing.</p>
How often do you struggle with procrastination?	Procrastination frequency	Multiple choice	Around 70% of respondents admitted to procrastinating several times a week, suggesting it is a widespread habit among students.
How many hours do you spend on academic work daily?	Study balance	Short answer	Over half of respondents study 4–6 hours per day, but nearly 30% felt their workload is “excessive,” showing imbalance.
What makes it difficult for you to maintain focus while studying?	Academic stress factors	Multiple choice	Most students identified multitasking, smartphone usage, and mental fatigue as major barriers to concentration.
Do you often feel isolated or unsupported during academic stress periods?	Loneliness and peer connection	Likert scale (1–5)	Over 60% rated 4 or 5, indicating strong feelings of isolation, especially during exam seasons or group deadlines.

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